

A study on potential donor sites of some substituted 1,2,4-triazoles and their denticity

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Manuscript received 20 November 2001, revised 3 May 2002, accepted 17 June 2002

4-Amino-5-(2'-hydroxy)phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (AHPMT) and its Schiff bases, viz. 4-benzylideneamino-5-(2'-hydroxy)phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (BHPMT) and 4-(2'-hydroxy)benzylideneamino-5-(2'-hydroxy)phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (HBHPMT) were synthesized. Proton-ligand and metal(II)-ligand constants ($M = \text{Co, Ni, Zn and Pb}$) of these ligands were determined in 70% (v/v) acetone-water and dioxan-water media at 0.1 M (KNO_3) ionic strength and 303 K temperature. The order of basicity corresponding to mercapto group was BHPMT > AHPMT > HBHPMT.

Schiff bases of triazoles are important class of ligands, and their complexing ability containing different donor atoms is reported¹. A survey of literature revealed no report on the study of dissociation and stability constants of metal chelates of 4-amino-5-(2'-hydroxy)phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (AHPMT), 4-benzylideneamino-5-(2'-hydroxy)phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (BHPMT) and 4-(2'-hydroxy)benzylideneamino-5-(2'-hydroxy)phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (HBHPMT). Therefore, it was thought to synthesize, characterize these ligands and study their potential donor sites to understand their chelating properties and the effect of solvents thereto.

Results and Discussion

The ligand AHPMT was prepared by the reported procedure. The purity of the ligand was checked by elemental analysis, IR, NMR, UV and mass spectra^{2,3}. The ligands BHPMT and HBHPMT were synthesized and characterized for the first time in our laboratory. BHPMT showed IR bands at 3092 (OH), 2933 (C-H), 1604 (C=N), 1160 (C=S) and 763, 738 and 692 cm^{-1} (C-H out-of-plane bending modes of mono and disubstituted benzenes). The IR spectrum of HBHPMT showed peaks at 3093 (OH), 2936 (C-H), 1621 (C=N), 1153 (C=S) and 764 cm^{-1} (out-of-plane C-H bending vibration of *ortho*-disubstituted-benzene). ¹H NMR spectrum of BHPMT in CDCl_3 -DMSO- d_6 showed signals at δ 14.0 (1H, s, SH), 9.93 (1H, s, OH), 9.64 (1H, s, azomethine CH) and 6.8–7.9 (9H, m, arom. CH), the signals corresponding to SH and OH readily exchanged with D_2O . The proton ¹H NMR spectrum of HBHPMT in DMSO- d_6 showed signals at δ 14.03 (1H, s, SH), 10.41

(1H, s, OH), 10.1 (1H, s, OH), 9.8 (1H, s, azomethine CH) and 6.97–7.62 (8H, m, arom. CH). The signals corresponding to two hydroxyl groups and thiol proton were identified by their ready exchange with D_2O . ¹³C NMR of BHPMT and HBHPMT showed fifteen signals indicating the presence of fifteen carbon atoms in these ligands. Mass spectra of BHPMT and HBHPMT displayed their corresponding molecular ion (M^+) peak at m/z 296 and 312, respectively. The $M^+ + 2$ peak due to presence of sulfur atom was also evident from the spectra.

Equilibrium studies :

The effects of solvent on the dissociation constants of AHPMT, BHPMT and HBHPMT and stability constants of their metal complexes were studied by determining pK_a and $\log K$ values of these ligands in 70% (v/v) acetone-water and dioxan-water media at 303 K and 0.1 M (KNO_3) ionic strength. AHPMT and BHPMT showed one dissociable proton corresponding to thiol group. HBHPMT showed two dissociable protons corresponding to thiol and hydroxyl groups, where deprotonation of second proton with higher pK_a value corresponded to hydroxyl group of (2-hydroxy)benzylideneamino group. The pK_a values of these ligands are higher in dioxan-water than in acetone-water medium (Table 1). The higher values of pK_a in dioxan-water are due to the low dielectric constant of the former medium⁴. The order of pK_a corresponding to thiol proton is BHPMT > AHPMT > HBHPMT. The lower value of dissociation constant in HBHPMT is due to the fact that the hydrogen bonding between benzylidene nitrogen and hydroxyl group dominates over the hydrogen bonding from thiol group. Hence, the proton dissociates easily in

HBHPMT than in BHPMT and AHPMT. The higher pK_a in BHPMT than in AHPMT is due to the presence of sp^2 hybridized nitrogen in BHPMT, which favors the strong hydrogen bonding than sp^3 hybridized nitrogen in AHPMT. The maximum value of \bar{n} for $M(II)$ -AHPMT in 70% (v/v) acetone-water media varied from 0.1 to 0.9, indicating formation of only 1 : 1 (ML) complexes except for Pb^{II} -AHPMT, where 1 : 2 complex is indicated. The n -values of $M(II)$ -AHPMT in dioxan-water, $M(II)$ -HBHPMT (except Pb^{II}) in acetone-water and $M(II)$ -BHPMT in acetone-water as well as dioxan-water media varied from 0.1 to 2.0, indicating the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. In HBHPMT system, only 1 : 1 complexes are formed with all metal ions in dioxan-water medium, and with Pb^{II} in acetone-water medium (Table 1). This indicates that AHPMT and BHPMT behave as bidentate ligands with N and S donor atoms, whereas HBHPMT acts as terdentate ligand with S, N and O donor sites.

Table 1. Dissociation constants and metal-ligand stability constants in 70%(v/v) acetone-water/dioxan-water medium

Temp = 30°, ionic strength = 0.1 M (KNO ₃)					
Ligand (Medium)	Form. const.	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Pb ^{II}
AHPMT (Acetone)	log K_1	4.3	4.35	5.65	6.11
	log K_2	—	—	—	4.15
7.42					
AHPMT (Dioxan)	log K_1	5.35	5.65	5.50	5.17
	log K_2	4.90	5.40	5.25	4.67
8.85					
BHPMT (Acetone)	log K_1	4.50	4.78	5.00	5.27
	log K_2	4.25	4.25	4.50	4.75
8.08					
BHPMT (Dioxan)	log K_1	6.05	6.64	6.51	7.45
	log K_2	4.96	5.80	5.85	5.56
9.4					
HBHPMT (Acetone)	log K_1	7.81	8.20	8.65	8.15
	log K_2	4.72	4.09	4.45	—
7.25, 9.53					
HBHPMT (Dioxan)	log K_1	9.06	9.52	9.45	8.36
8.53, 10.60					

Experimental

AHPMT was synthesized by following the reported procedure². Schiff bases BHPMT and HBHPMT were prepared by refluxing AHPMT and the corresponding aldehyde, viz. benzaldehyde and salicylaldehyde, in 1 : 1 molar ratio in acidic ethanol medium for 30 min. On cooling, the compounds separated were crystallized from ethanol. Purity of the compounds was checked by TLC (AHPMT, m.p. 204°; BHPMT, 212°; HBHPMT, 241°). IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 435 spectrophotometer, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra on a Bruker WH (270 MHz) spectrometer and mass spectra on a JEOL DX 300 spectrometer. All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Solutions for the potentiometric titrations were prepared in double-distilled water. Metal ion solutions were standardized by usual procedure⁵. The proton-ligand dissociation constant and metal-ligand formation constants for binary systems were determined potentiometrically using Irving-Rossotti pH-titration technique⁵. Experimental procedure for binary systems was the same as reported elsewhere⁷. pH was measured on a Digisum DI-707 pH-meter consisting of a combined glass electrode and calomel electrode.

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